

Study of Some Type of Matrix Fractional Integral

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Abstract: In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we find some type of matrix fractional integral by using some methods. In fact, our result is a generalization of traditional calculus result.

Keywords: New multiplication, fractional analytic functions, matrix fractional integral.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the applications of fractional calculus in various fields of science is growing rapidly, such as physics, biology, mechanics, electrical engineering, viscoelasticity, control theory, modelling, economics, etc [1-15]. However, the rule of fractional derivative is not unique, many scholars have given the definitions of fractional derivatives. The common definition is Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative. Other useful definitions include Caputo fractional derivative, Grunwald-Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivative, and Jumarie type of R-L fractional derivative to avoid non-zero fractional derivative of constant function [16-20].

In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we obtain the following matrix fractional integral:

$$({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[\left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} p} \otimes_{\alpha} E_{\alpha} \left(\left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} q} \right) \right],$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, p, q are positive integers, t is a real number, and A is a real matrix. Moreover, our result is a generalization of the result in ordinary calculus.

II. PRELIMINARIES

At first, we introduce the fractional calculus used in this paper.

Definition 2.1 ([21]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. The Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) α -fractional derivative is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)-f(x_0)}{(x-t)^\alpha} dt. \quad (1)$$

And the Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville α -fractional integral is defined by

$$({}_{x_0}I_x^\alpha)[f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad (2)$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function.

Definition 2.2 ([22]): If x, x_0 , and a_n are real numbers for all n , $x_0 \in (a, b)$, and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as an α -fractional power series, that is, $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x-x_0)^{n\alpha}$ on some open interval

containing x_0 , then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic at x_0 . Furthermore, if $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is continuous on closed interval $[a, b]$ and it is α -fractional analytic at every point in open interval (a, b) , then f_α is called an α -fractional analytic function on $[a, b]$.

In the following, we introduce a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions.

Definition 2.3 ([23]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Assume that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional power series at $x = x_0$,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad (3)$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \quad (4)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{n\alpha} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_m}{\Gamma(m\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^{m\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) (x - x_0)^{n\alpha}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} & f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{b_m}{m!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha m} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m} a_{n-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} (x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Definition 2.4 ([24]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and A is a matrix. The matrix α -fractional exponential function is defined by

$$E_\alpha(Ax^\alpha) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} A^n \frac{x^{n\alpha}}{\Gamma(n\alpha+1)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(A \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n}. \quad (7)$$

III. MAIN RESULT

In this section, we find some type of matrix fractional integral.

Theorem 3.1: Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, p, q be positive integers, t be a real number, and A be a matrix. Then

$$({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[\left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p} \otimes_\alpha E_\alpha \left(\left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha q} \right) \right] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!(nq+p+1)} (tA)^{nq+p} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (nq+p+1)}. \quad (8)$$

Proof

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[\left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p} \otimes_\alpha E_\alpha \left(\left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha q} \right) \right] \\ &= ({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[\left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(\left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha q} \right)^{\otimes_\alpha n} \right] \\ &= ({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[\left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha p} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha nq} \right] \\ &= ({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (nq+p)} \right] \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} ({}_0 I_x^\alpha) \left[\left(tA \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (nq+p)} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} (tA)^{nq+p} \left({}_0I_x^\alpha \right) \left[\left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (nq+p)} \right] \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!(nq+p+1)} (tA)^{nq+p} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_{\alpha} (nq+p+1)}. \quad \text{q.e.d.}
\end{aligned}$$

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we evaluate some type of matrix fractional integral. In fact, our result is a generalization of classical calculus result. In the future, we will continue to use the new multiplication of fractional analytic functions to solve the problems in applied mathematics and fractional differential equations.

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